

A Systematic Review of Enhancing CNN Performance in Automated Fabric Defect Detection Through Sampling Techniques

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Abstract

In the textile industry, manual fabric inspection presents several significant challenges. Inaccurate or incomplete inspections can lead to increased costs and reduced product quality. With the rise of deep learning, various machine learning algorithms have proven effective in tasks such as image classification and analysis. However, key challenges remain, including the complexity and time-consuming nature of training processes, the demand for large datasets, and difficulties in achieving model generalization. There is a clear need for a fast and accurate machine learning algorithm capable of real-time defect detection in industrial environments.

To address these issues, this research introduces a simple yet effective Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)-based machine learning model. The performance of the model was assessed using two different image resolutions: 150x700 and 245x345. The findings revealed that image size has a significant impact on performance. Furthermore, the effectiveness of the model was hindered by the imbalance of the data set, which caused poor training and overfitting.

To mitigate the effects of data set imbalance and improve performance, several sampling techniques were tested. Among these, the combination of the CNN model with a smaller image size (245x345) and the SMOTEENN sampling technique yielded the best results. This configuration achieved impressive performance metrics, including 98.00%. The study also outlines a deployment strategy to integrate the proposed model into an automated quality inspection system for the textile industry.

KEYWORDS: Fabric defect detection, deep learning, convolutional neural networks, textile inspection, computer vision, machine learning, automated quality control.

Abbreviations

The following is a list of abbreviations and acronyms used throughout this study for quick reference: (3)

CNN	<i>Convolutional Neural Network</i> : A type of deep learning model commonly used for image recognition and classification tasks.
TP	<i>True Positive</i> : Cases correctly identified as positive by the model.
FP	<i>False Positive</i> : Cases incorrectly identified as positive.
TN	<i>True Negative</i> : Cases correctly identified as negative.
FN	<i>False Negative</i> : Cases incorrectly identified as negative.
p	<i>Precision</i> : The proportion of true positive predictions among all positive predictions.
r	<i>Recall</i> : The proportion of true positive predictions among all actual positives.
SSD	<i>Single Shot Detector</i> : A real-time object detection algorithm.
VLSTM	<i>Visual Long Short-Term Memory</i> : A model combining visual data processing with temporal sequence learning.
VP	<i>Visual Perception</i> : The system's ability to interpret visual inputs.
SCAE	<i>Stacked Convolutional Autoencoders</i> : A deep learning technique for unsupervised feature extraction.
R-CNN	<i>Region-Based Convolutional Neural Network</i> : A model for object detection that identifies regions of interest before classification.
RPN	<i>Region Proposal Network</i> : A component of R-CNN that proposes candidate object regions.
ROI	<i>Region of Interest</i> : The specific area in an image that is being analyzed or classified.
PRAN-Net	<i>Priori Anchor Convolutional Neural Network</i> : A neural network that uses predefined anchor boxes to improve detection accuracy.

MSCNN with K-clustering	<i>Multi-Scale CNN with K-means Clustering</i> : An approach combining multiscale feature learning with clustering techniques.
CBAM	<i>Convolutional Block Attention Module</i> : A mechanism that helps neural networks focus on important features in images.
ROC	<i>Receiver Operating Characteristic</i> : Graphite used to evaluate the performance of classification models.
ReLU	<i>Rectified Linear Unit</i> : A widely used activation function in neural networks.
ADASYN	<i>Adaptive Synthetic Sampling</i> : A technique used to address class imbalance by generating synthetic examples.
SMOTE	<i>Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique</i> : Another approach for dealing with imbalanced datasets is by creating synthetic samples.
PCA	<i>Principal Component Analysis</i> : A method for reducing the dimensionality of datasets while preserving important information.

Introduction

A textile fabric manufacturing process is depicted in Fig. 1 below:

Fiber → Spinning → Yarn → Weaving → Greige Fabric → Dyeing → Finished Fabric → Stitching → Cutting

Figure 1: Fabric manufacturing process

Fabric Inspection

Fabric inspection is performed at each stage of the textile manufacturing process, including weaving, dyeing, printing, and finishing. This ensures product quality and minimizes potential losses (Li et al., 2021, p. 1) (3). The structure of fabric is inherently repetitive; therefore, any defects disrupt this repetitive pattern (Gandelsman, Shocher, and Irani, 2019, as cited in Wang and Jing, 2020, p. 161318) (10). Early defect detection is crucial to prevent wastage in the final product (Bullon et al., 2017, as cited in Li et al., 2021, p. 1). Jing et al. (2022, pp. 2-3) (22) categorized the task of defect detection into four levels.

- The first level involves the task of classifying defects into categories;

- The second level involves detecting and locating these defects;
- The third level identifies defective pixels within images, known as segmentation;
- The fourth level entails defect semantic segmentation, combining segmentation and classification.

Fabric defect detection algorithms can be categorized into two types:

- Traditional algorithms and
- Learning-based algorithms.

Traditional algorithms include statistical, spectral, structural, and model-based methods. These techniques process individual images and require manual feature selection. In contrast, learning-based methods automate feature selection. Learning-based algorithms can be further divided into the following:

- Classical machine learning algorithms;
- Deep machine learning algorithms

Deep learning methods have the advantage of automatic feature extraction; however, they often require a substantial amount of data compared to classical machine learning algorithms, which, in turn, require extensive parameter tuning (Li et al., 2021, pp. 1-2; Wang and Jing, 2020, p. 161317) (27).

Research has shown that CNN predictions for face recognition, image classification, and real-time object detection can be as accurate as humans (Du, 2018; Fan and Zhou, 2016) (32).

Related Works

Liu et al. (2018) (38) introduced an improved approach that modified the Single Shot Detector (SSD) by incorporating a shallower convolutional feature layer. Their method integrated the single detection capabilities of deep neural networks with the regression mechanism of YOLO and the anchor concept from Faster R-CNN. The use of regression streamlined the algorithm, enhancing its efficiency, while anchors were utilized to better represent various scales and aspect ratios. Additionally, SSD applied a multiscale object feature extraction strategy. Despite these advancements, the method faced difficulties in reliably detecting small defects.

Zhang et al. (2018) (44) carried out a comparative analysis of the YOLO 9000, YOLO-VOC (10), and Tiny YOLO models, ultimately developing an enhanced version of the YOLO-VOC model. This improved model incorporated superparameter optimization to enhance defect classification and localization. By leveraging a single-stage CNN for image prediction, the method achieved higher detection speed. However, the accuracy of the proposed approach was relatively

lower in comparison to other models.

According to a study referenced by Minhas and Zelek (2020, p. 507), Tan et al. (2018) (47) highlighted network-based transfer learning as the most effective approach among various transfer learning methods, including instance-based and mapping-based techniques. This method involves creating a target network by adapting a source network, which comprises feature extraction and classification sub-networks. This strategy is particularly beneficial for defect classification tasks where labeled data is limited.

Liu et al. (2019, p. 2) (44) highlighted the effectiveness of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) in achieving high accuracy for fabric defect detection. Similarly, Prakash et al. (2021) recognized deep learning, particularly CNNs, as a powerful machine learning approach for image detection and multi-classification tasks, noting its suitability for real-time applications.

Zhao et al. (2019) (50) developed a classification model that combined a visual Long-Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network [5] with a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), leveraging visual perception (VP) for improved performance. The model utilized Stacked Convolutional Auto encoders (SCAEs) for feature extraction. Experimental evaluations on datasets with 500, 1,000, and 10,500 images revealed the best performance on the 500-image dataset, achieving an accuracy of 99.47% Liu et al. (2019) (44) introduced LZFFNet, an optimized version of the VGG16 convolutional network integrated with a deconvolutional network for precise defect detection. This model featured a deconvolutional network linked to each VGG16 layer, enabling a seamless pathway back to the image pixel space. Although the model required relatively few parameters, acquiring a large volume of labeled training data for CNN models in practical applications posed a significant challenge.

Wei et al. (2019) (57) presented a Faster R-CNN model designed for fabric defect detection, comprising convolutional layers, a Region Proposal Network (RPN), ROI pooling, and a classification layer. The model utilized VGG16 for feature extraction, with the classification layer outputting background scores for each anchor and the regression layer providing defect coordinates. Despite its effectiveness, the method faced challenges due to prolonged training times. Building on this, Chen et al. (2020) enhanced the Faster R-CNN model by integrating Gabor kernels and employing a two-stage backpropagation training approach, improving its performance.

Minhas and Zelek (2020) developed a specialized VGG16 model (50) enhanced with deconvolutional networks and optimized using transfer learning. Their study focused on two key approaches: fixed feature extraction and full network fine-tuning. The latter, which updates all network parameters during training, demonstrated superior performance compared to fixed feature extraction. However, the research did not address the detection speed of the model.

Peng et al. (2020) proposed the Priori Anchor Convolutional Neural Network (PRAN-Net) (59), designed to achieve high accuracy in detecting small defects. The model employed multi-scale feature maps generated by a Feature Pyramid Network (FPN) to create sparse priori anchors aligned with the ground truth boxes of fabric defects. ResNet-101-FPN was utilized for feature extraction,

enhancing the model’s capability for precise defect detection.

Zhao et al. (2020) adopted a K-means clustering technique called Multi-scale CNN with K-clustering (MSCNN with K-clustering) (61) to define defect bounding boxes with predefined sizes. While effective, this data-driven approach necessitates a large dataset of labeled fabric images for training and is limited to detecting only five types of defects.

Almeida, Moutinho, and Matos-Carvalho (2021) (65) developed an operator-assisted CNN model designed to address the cost implications of classification errors, prioritizing the reduction of False Negatives (FNs) over False Positives (FPs). The model initially achieved an average accuracy of 75%. He et al. (2021) proposed an enhanced Faster R-CNN algorithm (7) that integrated the Convolutional Block Attention Module (CBAM) with ResNet50 for improved feature extraction. ResNet50 was used for feature extraction, classification, and regression, with the extracted feature map fed into RoI pooling and the Region Proposal Network (RPN). To reduce redundant boxes, Soft-NMS and RPN were utilized. This model can be combined with CNN and trained end-to-end with the basic CNN. Although the method is computationally intensive, the Channel Attention Module reduces the spatial dimension of the feature map, compressing it into a one-dimensional vector before further processing.

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) Model

The CNN algorithm has demonstrated remarkable success in object identification within images (Walleign et al., 2018) (72) and was therefore utilized in the current study. As described by Yamashita et al. (2018, pp. 612-617) [14], a standard CNN architecture includes convolution layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers. It utilizes a kernel, a small parameter grid, to process input tensors. The kernel slides over the input tensor, computing the product of its elements with the corresponding input elements and summing the results to produce a feature map. Key hyperparameters in this process include the size and number of kernels. Padding is also crucial, as it adjusts the dimensions of the output feature map by overlapping the kernel’s center with the outermost elements of the input tensor.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are composed of convolution layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers, forming the foundation of their architecture (Yamashita et al., 2018, p. 612) (72). The convolution layer serves as the core feature extraction component, leveraging a kernel—a small parameter grid—for processing the image, typically stored as a two-dimensional (2D) grid of pixels (Yamashita et al., 2018, p. 612) .

The hierarchical design allows extracted features to progressively become more complex as the output of one layer feeds into the next. During training, the model minimizes the difference between its output and the ground truth using backpropagation and gradient descent, enabling the kernels to learn automatically. Critical hyperparameters that require tuning include kernel size, the

Figure 2

number of kernels, padding, and stride (Yamashita et al., 2018, p. 612) .

Convolution, a linear operation, applies the kernel to the input tensor by computing and summing the product of corresponding elements, resulting in a feature map (73). Common kernel sizes are 3×3 , 5×5 , and 7×7 (Yamashita et al., 2018, p. 614). Padding helps preserve the spatial dimensions of the feature map by aligning the kernel’s center with the input tensor’s edges (Yamashita et al., 2018, p. 614). Stride, which determines the step size between kernel applications, can be increased to downsample feature maps efficiently (Yamashita et al., 2018, p. 614) .

Nonlinear activation function

The outputs of linear operations like convolution are processed through nonlinear activation functions to introduce nonlinearity into the model. Common activation functions include sigmoid, hyperbolic tangent (tanh), and rectified linear unit (ReLU) functions (Yamashita et al., 2018, p. 615) .

Pooling layers

Pooling layers play a crucial role in reducing the dimensionality of feature maps, thereby decreasing the number of learnable parameters in subsequent layers (Yamashita et al., 2018, p. 615) . Weight sharing serves several purposes:

- Pattern detection across images: It enables kernels to apply local feature patterns across all images for pattern recognition.
- Learning spatial hierarchies: When combined with pooling operations, it helps in downsampling, which captures larger fields of view to learn spatial hierarchies of feature patterns.
- Enhanced model efficiency: It reduces the number of parameters compared to fully connected networks, making the model more efficient.

Max pooling, a common pooling technique, extracts patches from the input feature map and retains only the maximum value from each patch. Typically, a

2×2 filter with a stride of 2 is used, reducing the feature map's dimensions by half (Yamashita et al., 2018, pp. 615–616) .

Fully connected layer

The output feature maps from the final convolution or pooling layer are transformed into a one-dimensional (1D) array through flattening. This 1D array is then passed to one or more fully connected layers, also referred to as dense layers. In dense layers, each input is connected to every output via learnable weights. The final fully connected layer generally has an output node count equivalent to the number of target classes. Nonlinear activation functions, such as ReLU, are typically applied after each fully connected layer to introduce nonlinearity (Yamashita et al., 2018, p. 616) .

Last layer activation function

Choosing an appropriate activation function for the final fully connected layer is critical and should align with the specific task. For multiclass classification tasks, the SoftMax function is widely used. This function transforms the output values from the final fully connected layer into probabilities for each target class. It ensures that all output values are normalized to fall between 0 and 1, with their total summing up to 1, making it suitable for probabilistic interpretation (Yamashita et al., 2018, p. 616).

Data and ground truth labels

To train and evaluate a model, data along with ground truth labels are gathered and then divided into three subsets: a training set, a validation set, and a test set. The training set is used to fit the model, the validation set helps tune hyper parameters and prevent overfitting, and the test set assesses the model's final performance (Yamashita et al., 2018, p. 617).

Overfitting

Overfitting occurs when a model learns irrelevant patterns from the training data instead of the underlying signal, leading to poor performance on new datasets. An overfitted model fails to generalize effectively to unseen data. Signs of overfitting include a significant performance gap between the training and validation sets.

The most effective way to address overfitting is by increasing the amount of training data. Other methods include dropout, batch normalization, data augmentation, and reducing model complexity.

- Dropout involves randomly setting activations to zero during training, preventing reliance on specific weights.
- Weight decay penalizes large weights, discouraging over-complex models.
- Batch normalization normalizes input values in each layer, improving gradient flow and allowing for faster learning rates.
- Data augmentation creates diverse training samples by applying transformations like flipping, translation, and rotation, exposing the model to varied input data.

These techniques collectively enhance generalization and mitigate overfitting (Yamashita et al., 2018, pp. 619-620) .

Loss function or Cost Function

Loss functions are used to measure the compatibility between the output predictions of a neural network and the given ground truth labels. For multiclass classification tasks, the cross-entropy loss function is commonly employed as it evaluates how well the predicted probability distribution aligns with the true class labels (Yamashita et al., 2018, pp. 617).

The ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) activation function operates by applying weights to input values and summing them to generate outputs. It is widely used in CNNs due to its simplicity and effectiveness in avoiding the vanishing gradient problem, which is prevalent in activation functions like sigmoid or hyperbolic tangent when used in multi-layered CNNs (Yamashita et al., 2018, pp. 612-617).

The Adaptive Moment Estimation (Adam) optimizer, as noted by Prakash et al. (2021, p. 4), is frequently used to minimize error loss due to its efficiency in handling sparse gradients and noisy data. Similarly, Gradient Descent is employed to iteratively update the learnable parameters of the network (84), such as kernels and weights, in a direction that minimizes the loss function, thereby improving the model's accuracy (Yamashita et al., 2018, pp. 619-620) .

Gradient descent

Gradient Descent is used to update the learning parameters (such as weights and biases) of the network to minimize the loss function. This process iteratively adjusts the parameters in the direction that reduces the difference between the predicted and actual outputs, thus improving the model's performance (Yamashita et al., 2018, pp. 617) .

Epochs in Deep Learning

An epoch in neural network training refers to one complete pass through the entire training dataset. During each epoch, the model adjusts its parameters (weights and biases) by applying the chosen optimization algorithm to minimize the loss function. Data is passed through the network, and the model makes predictions. These predictions are compared with the actual values, and the loss is computed. Techniques like backpropagation are used to calculate the gradients of the loss, guiding the updates to the model's parameters. The optimization algorithm, such as stochastic gradient descent (SGD), updates the parameters to reduce the loss (1). This process is repeated for each data batch until all batches are processed, completing one epoch. Multiple epochs are typically used to allow the model to learn from the entire dataset. The number of epochs is a hyperparameter that is adjusted during training and validation to balance model performance and computational efficiency (LeCun et al., 1998) .

Test and Validation Set

In machine learning, the dataset is typically divided into three subsets: the training set, validation set, and test set.

1. **Training Set:** This is the data used to train the model. The model learns the relationships between the input features and the target variable through iterative optimization on this dataset. The training set allows the model to fit and learn the parameters that minimize the loss function.
2. **Validation Set:** This set is used to tune the model's hyperparameters and evaluate its performance during the training process. It helps detect issues like overfitting by providing feedback on how well the model is performing on unseen data during training. By evaluating the model on the validation set, one can adjust the model architecture, modify hyperparameters, or apply regularization techniques. The validation set provides an unbiased assessment of the model's performance during training, helping guide model selection (2).
3. **Test Set:** After training and hyperparameter tuning, the model is evaluated on the test set. This set is not used during training or validation, making it a final, unbiased evaluation of the model's performance. The test set simulates how the model would perform on unseen data (3). The performance metrics from the test set provide a realistic estimate of the model's generalization ability, which is critical for assessing the model's effectiveness in real-world applications.

These three sets help ensure that the model is not only well-tuned and optimized for the data it has seen but also capable of performing well on new, unseen data (Goodfellow, Bengio, and Courville, 2016).

Imbalance Dataset and Resampling Techniques

An imbalanced dataset occurs when the classification categories have unequal distribution, meaning that one class has significantly more samples than the other (4). In such cases, accuracy becomes a less useful performance measure because a model could achieve high accuracy by simply predicting the majority class, but this wouldn't indicate its true ability to detect the minority class.

To address this issue, resampling techniques can be applied to balance the dataset. These techniques aim to adjust the distribution of classes by either oversampling the minority class or undersampling the majority class, helping to ensure that the model is trained on a more balanced representation of the data. By doing so, the model is less likely to be biased toward the majority class and can better recognize patterns related to the minority class (86).

According to Chawla et al. (2002), balancing the dataset is crucial to avoid bias and systematic error in the model's predictions. As Howarth et al. (2020) [18] point out, a balanced dataset, where the sample sizes of both positive and negative examples are roughly equivalent, is necessary for improving model performance and ensuring the results are not skewed towards one class.

Data Sampling

An imbalanced dataset can be categorized into two types: absolute imbalance and relative imbalance (Letteri et al., 2020, pp. 3-4) (42).

1. Absolute Imbalance:

- This occurs when the minority class has fewer samples and is not adequately represented within the dataset. The number of samples in the minority class is much smaller than in the majority class.

2. Relative Imbalance:

- In this case, the minority class is better represented than in absolute imbalance, but its sample count is still larger than that of the majority class, leading to an imbalance.

Imbalance can also be characterized by:

1. Between-Class Imbalance:

- This occurs when the number of samples representing one class is significantly different from the number of samples representing the other class.

2. Within-Class Imbalance:

- This happens when a class is made up of multiple subclusters, each containing a different number of samples. The imbalance exists

within the class itself, rather than between different classes (Letteri et al., 2020, pp. 3-4) (42).

Both types of imbalance can introduce challenges in machine learning tasks and often require techniques such as resampling or synthetic data generation to address the issues effectively.

Problems of Data Imbalance

Class imbalance can introduce several challenges in machine learning:

- **Bias towards Majority Class:** The classifier tends to favor the majority class due to its dominance in the dataset, leading to poor performance in predicting the minority class.
- **Hindered Minority Class Recognition:** When there are insufficient samples from the minority class, the classifier struggles to learn the decision boundary between the classes, making it difficult to accurately identify instances of the minority class.
- **Impact of Noisy Data:** Imbalanced datasets are more vulnerable to noisy data, as the few minority class samples may be overshadowed by noise and outliers in the majority class, further degrading model performance (Letteri et al., 2020, pp. 4) (42).

To address class imbalance, resampling techniques are often applied to adjust the class distribution. This can involve either oversampling the minority class or undersampling the majority class to ensure a more balanced dataset, allowing the model to better learn the distinguishing characteristics of all classes (Letteri et al., 2020, pp. 4) (42).

Imbalanced Dataset Approaches

Resampling techniques, including oversampling and under sampling, are commonly used to address class imbalance in datasets (Letteri et al., 2020, p. 4) (42). Jing et al. (2020, p. 3) (36) categorized methods to tackle class imbalance into hard and soft sampling techniques. Hard sampling methods involve down-sampling either the positive or negative class samples to balance the dataset, whereas soft sampling methods apply a weighted loss function, which updates the model parameters using the entire dataset while adjusting the influence of different classes.

In fabric defect detection, Rasheed et al. (2020, p. 2) (61) highlighted the challenges of acquiring well-balanced datasets, particularly in the context of fabric defects. They noted that class imbalance could significantly hinder the performance of traditional machine learning algorithms. To address this, mean average precision and the ROC curve were found to be better evaluation metrics

for imbalanced datasets, as they provide a more nuanced view of model performance, especially when dealing with rare events like fabric defects (Rasheed et al., 2020, p. 20) (61).

To overcome issues related to class imbalance, Lin et al. (2023, pp. 2-10) (46) introduced the generalized focal loss function, which helps the model focus more on learning positive samples while minimizing the influence of negative samples that carry less useful information. On the other hand, Jing et al. (2020) (36) proposed using the median frequency loss function, which adjusts the loss based on the frequency of the classes to address imbalance.

Further advancing techniques in deep learning for detecting fabric defects, Cheng et al. (2022, pp. 3101-3122) (13) proposed a Separation Convolution UNet (SCUNet), an enhanced version of the original UNet designed for medical image segmentation. SCUNet improved upon UNet by addressing issues like information loss during down-sampling and overfitting. Unlike UNet, which used max-pooling to reduce feature map size, SCUNet employed convolutional down-sampling, which preserved more information. SCUNet also replaced traditional convolutions with depth-separable convolutions to reduce the number of parameters while enhancing feature extraction. Additionally, SCUNet used the Intersection over Union (IoU) loss function, which is more suited for handling irregular boundaries, such as those seen in fabric defects. The SCUNet model demonstrated impressive performance, with an accuracy of 98.01

Resampling Techniques

The most common methods to address class imbalance are:

1. **Oversampling:** This technique involves increasing the number of samples in the minority class, making the number of samples in each class more equal or closer to balanced. This helps to avoid the dominance of the majority class (Vladimir, 2020) (23).
2. **Undersampling:** In this method, some samples from the majority class are removed to balance the dataset. However, this can result in the loss of valuable data points from the majority class, potentially leading to a less representative model (Letteri et al., 2020, pp. 5) (42). To address this limitation, various advanced techniques are employed to mitigate the negative effects of data loss. Some of these techniques include:
 - **Cluster-based Undersampling:** Instead of removing random samples from the majority class, this method clusters the majority class samples and then selects a representative sample from each cluster to retain the diversity of the majority class while reducing its size.
 - **NearMiss:** A technique where undersampling is done by removing the majority class samples that are farthest from the decision boundary, focusing on keeping those samples that are closest to the minority class samples.

- **Edited Nearest Neighbors (ENN):** This method removes samples from the majority class that are misclassified by their nearest neighbors, ensuring that only useful samples remain.

By using these methods, both oversampling and undersampling help to address the issue of class imbalance and improve model performance, particularly in tasks where one class is significantly underrepresented.

Imbalanced-learn Tool

Imbalanced-learn is a Python package designed to help tackle the challenges posed by imbalanced datasets. It offers a variety of methods for data preprocessing, such as:

- **Oversampling:** Increasing the number of minority class samples.
- **Undersampling:** Reducing the number of majority class samples.
- **Combination of Oversampling and Undersampling:** A hybrid approach that applies both techniques to achieve a balanced dataset.
- **Ensemble Sampling:** Combines multiple sampling methods to improve model robustness and performance.

The package also features a category labeled *Miscellaneous*, which includes techniques like *Function Sampler*, allowing users to apply custom sampling strategies.

Instance Selection Algorithms

Instance selection algorithms aim to eliminate unimportant or redundant samples from the dataset. By selecting a subset of the data that preserves the underlying distribution, these algorithms ensure that the remaining data is still representative of the overall dataset's characteristics. This technique helps to reduce noise and improve the model's performance by focusing on the most informative samples (Letteri et al., 2020, pp. 5) (42).

Combination Method

The Ensemble Method combines multiple weak classifiers to create a stronger, more comprehensive classifier. This approach often results in improved performance, as it leverages the strengths of each individual classifier and mitigates their weaknesses. The combined classifier typically performs better than any of the individual models, making it a powerful tool in addressing issues like class imbalance (Duan et al., 2020, p.1-2) (19).

Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique SMOTE

SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Over-Sampling Technique) is an over-sampling technique used to balance imbalanced datasets by generating synthetic examples for the minority class. This method creates new data points that are similar but slightly different from the existing minority class instances. The process works as follows:

1. A minority class instance is selected at random.
2. The k-nearest neighbors of this instance are identified.
3. One of these k-nearest neighbors is chosen at random.
4. A synthetic example is created by interpolating between the selected instance and its neighbor.

This technique helps to increase the diversity of the minority class and improve the model's ability to learn from these underrepresented data points (Chawla et al., 2002, pp. 328; Pahren et al., 2022, pp. 75) (11).

Random over-sampling

The method you're describing is Random Oversampling, a technique used to balance imbalanced datasets. It involves selecting samples from the minority class at random and duplicating them to increase the number of minority class samples. This process continues until the dataset achieves a more balanced distribution between the majority and minority classes. When dealing with multiple classes, random oversampling is applied independently to each class. The key characteristic of this method is that it introduces repeated samples of the minority class, which may help improve model performance, but it can also increase the risk of overfitting (imbalanced-learn, n.d., i).

Borderline SMOTE

The technique you're describing is Borderline-SMOTE. This method is an extension of the SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Over-Sampling Technique) that specifically focuses on generating synthetic samples for the borderline instances of the minority class. These borderline instances are the samples that are closest to the decision boundary separating the minority and majority classes. The rationale behind Borderline-SMOTE is that these borderline samples are more informative for the model, as they lie near the region where the class distinction is most critical. By generating synthetic samples around these borderline instances, the model is encouraged to

learn more robust decision boundaries, which can improve its performance on imbalanced datasets (Han et al., 2005) (27).

SMOTENC (Synthetic Minority Over-Sampling Technique for Nominal and Continuous):

- This method is designed to handle datasets with both continuous and nominal (categorical) features.
- It calculates the median of the standard deviations of the minority class in continuous features and uses Euclidean distance to find the k-nearest neighbors for synthetic sample generation (Chawla et al., 2002) [17].

SMOTEN (Synthetic Minority Over-Sampling Technique for Nominal):

- Specifically used for categorical data features, SMOTEN modifies the process by using the Value Difference Metric (VDM) to compute distances between feature values.
- The VDM looks at how feature values overlap across different feature vectors and creates a matrix to define the distance between corresponding feature values for all feature vectors (Chawla et al., 2002) (27).

SVM SMOTE:

- This variation uses a Support Vector Machine (SVM) to select samples for synthetic sample generation.
- In SVM SMOTE, the decision boundary is determined by the support vectors after training the SVM classifier on the original dataset (Imbalanced-learn, n.d.).

Drawbacks of SMOTE:

- Within-class imbalance: SMOTE does not address the imbalance within the minority class itself. It generates synthetic samples regardless of their proximity to the decision boundary, which can lead to creating samples far from the border, potentially exacerbating the imbalance.

Figure 3

- **Class Overlap:** The method can generate synthetic samples that overlap with the majority class, making the decision boundary even more ambiguous (Letteri et al., 2020; Duan et al., 2020) (19). This can reduce the overall effectiveness of the model as it may struggle to distinguish between classes.

Adaptive Synthetic (ADASYN) Algorithm:

The ADASYN algorithm is similar to SMOTE but adapts by generating a different number of synthetic samples based on the local distribution of the minority class. ADASYN introduces a random value, resulting in somewhat scattered samples (Letteri et al., 2020, p. 6-7) (42). It focuses on generating more samples where the minority class is harder to learn, addressing the learning bias caused by the imbalanced dataset. This adaptive approach shifts the decision boundary to focus on the difficult-to-learn samples, enhancing model performance on challenging cases (He et al., 2008, p. 1323) (30).

K-Means SMOTE Oversampling:

The K-Means SMOTE method operates in three stages:

- It clusters the entire input space using K-means clustering.
- Samples are then distributed:
 - Select clusters with a high number of minority class samples.
 - Assign more synthetic samples to clusters where minority class samples are sparse. This method combines SMOTE with random oversampling, treating them as the limit cases for sample distribution (kmeanssmote.readthedocs.io, n.d.).

Under sampling Methods:

- (a) **Cluster Centroids:** This technique reduces the influence of the majority class by replacing some of its samples with centroids generated using the K-means algorithm. A set number of majority class samples are selected, and K-means is applied to form clusters. These samples are then substituted by the cluster centroids (imbalanced-learn, n.d., b).
- (b) **Condensed Nearest Neighbor (CNN):** The Condensed Nearest Neighbor method reduces the dataset for k-NN classification by using a subset of examples. It operates as follows (Gowda and Krishna, 1979, p. 488) (Gowda and Krishna):
 - i. Collect all minority class samples into a set.
 - ii. Add a sample from the targeted class.
 - iii. Classify each sample using the nearest neighbor rule.
 - iv. Add a sample if it is misclassified.
 - v. Repeat the procedure until no misclassified samples remain.
- (c) **Edited Nearest Neighbor (ENN):** This method removes samples that are close to the decision boundary, improving dataset quality. Each sample is classified using the nearest neighbor rule, and any sample close to the decision boundary is removed (Wilson, 1972, p. 408) (77).
- (d) **Repeated Edited Nearest Neighbor (RENN):** Repeated ENN runs the Edited Nearest Neighbor method multiple times to further refine the dataset (imbalanced-learn, n.d., d).

Evaluation Metrics

0.1 Confusion Matrix

A confusion matrix is a tabular representation used to evaluate the performance of classification models. In this matrix, the rows represent the actual classes, while the columns indicate the predicted classes. It consists of the following components:

- **True Negative (TN):** The number of negative instances correctly predicted as negative.
- **False Positive (FP):** The number of negative instances incorrectly predicted as positive.
- **False Negative (FN):** The number of positive instances incorrectly predicted as negative.
- **True Positive (TP):** The number of positive instances correctly predicted as positive.

0.2 Performance Metrics

To evaluate classification models, especially in image recognition tasks, common performance indicators include accuracy, precision, recall, and the F1-score .

0.2.1 Accuracy

Accuracy measures the proportion of total predictions that the model classifies correctly. It is defined as:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\sum TP_i}{N} \quad (1)$$

where TP_i represents the number of correctly predicted instances for class i , and N denotes the total number of predictions

0.2.2 Precision

Precision indicates the proportion of positive identifications that are actually correct. It is calculated as:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (2)$$

This metric reflects the model's ability to return relevant results only .

0.2.3 Recall

Also known as sensitivity or the true positive rate, recall measures the ability of the model to identify all relevant instances. It is expressed as:

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (3)$$

A higher recall indicates the model is effectively capturing all actual positive cases .

0.2.4 F1-Score

The F1-score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall and is particularly useful when a balance between the two is needed. It is computed as:

$$\text{F1-score} = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (4)$$

The F1-score is beneficial in scenarios where data is imbalanced, as it considers both false positives and false negatives .

0.3 Considerations for Imbalanced Datasets

While accuracy is a widely used metric, it can be misleading in the context of imbalanced datasets. For instance, if a model correctly predicts all majority class instances but fails to detect the minority class, it may still yield a high accuracy. This makes accuracy an unreliable indicator in such situations (?).

For balanced datasets, an alternative metric is the error rate:

$$\text{Error Rate} = 1 - \text{Accuracy} \tag{5}$$

However, in the case of imbalanced data, precision and recall offer more insightful evaluation measures, providing a clearer picture of the classifier’s performance with respect to minority classes .

Data Visualization

Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a widely used statistical technique for reducing the dimensionality of high-dimensional datasets. It works by identifying the directions—known as principal components—along which the variance in the data is maximized. These directions serve as new axes for representing the data in a lower-dimensional space.

By projecting the data onto these principal components, PCA enables visualization of similarities and differences among data points, facilitating pattern discovery and grouping. Each principal component is a linear combination of the original features, meaning that PCA generates new, uncorrelated variables from the existing ones. This process helps in eliminating less informative features while preserving the most significant patterns of variance, thereby supporting feature extraction and data interpretation .

Visual Studio Code

Visual Studio Code (VS Code) is a lightweight yet powerful source-code editor developed by Microsoft. Although it is technically a code editor, it offers numerous features typically found in full-fledged integrated development environments (IDEs). It supports a broad array of programming languages and frameworks, making it suitable for various software development tasks.

Some of its notable features include syntax highlighting, intelligent code completion (IntelliSense), built-in Git integration, debugging tools, and a rich extension ecosystem. These capabilities make VS Code a preferred tool among developers for efficient and productive coding workflows .

TensorFlow and Keras

TensorFlow is an open-source framework developed by Google for building and training machine learning and deep learning models. It provides a compre-

hensive suite of libraries and tools to support the development of advanced AI applications. TensorFlow is widely adopted due to its scalability and flexibility across various platforms and environments .

Keras, initially developed by François Chollet, is a high-level neural network API written in Python. It is designed to be user-friendly, modular, and extensible, which allows for rapid prototyping of deep learning models. As of TensorFlow version 2.0, Keras has become the official high-level API integrated within TensorFlow.

Keras simplifies the process of building neural networks by offering intuitive building blocks such as layers, activation functions, loss functions, and optimizers. It supports various neural network architectures, including convolutional and recurrent networks, and is widely used for both research and production applications .

Research Questions

This study aims to explore and address the following research questions:

- **Feasibility:** Is it possible to develop a deep learning-based approach for fabric defect detection that ensures:
 - high processing speed,
 - enhanced detection accuracy, and
 - robust training across a diverse range of fabric defect types?
- **Balanced Detection:** Can such a method effectively minimize false negatives, thereby achieving a balanced and reliable detection performance?

The investigation primarily focuses on the application of deep learning techniques. Despite significant advancements in this area, current solutions still face notable limitations. A comprehensive system that fulfills all key performance criteria for practical industrial deployment has yet to be realized.

Materials and Methods

Dataset

Multiple publicly available and author-provided datasets were utilized in this study to create a comprehensive dataset for fabric defect detection. The sources of the datasets include:

- **Fabric Defect Dataset** from Kaggle, provided by Ranathunga (2020).
- **Fabric Stain Dataset** from Kaggle, contributed by Pathirana (2020).
- **AITEX Fabric Image Database** (Silvestre-Blanes et al., 2019).
- **Dataset from Peng et al. (2020)** — containing only non-defective fabric images, obtained with author consent.

AITEX Fabric Image Database

This dataset includes 245 textile fabric images representing 7 different fabric types. Each image has a resolution of 4096×256 pixels. It contains 140 defect-free images (20 for each fabric type) and 105 defective images distributed across multiple defect types .

Fabric Stain Dataset

Sourced from Kaggle, this dataset was created as part of a fabric defect detection project at the Intelligence Lab, University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka. The dataset includes 398 stained fabric images and 68 defect-free samples. Image resolutions are either 1920×1080 or 1080×1920 pixels.

Fabric Defect Dataset

Also from Kaggle, this dataset was provided by the Intelligence Lab, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, University of Moratuwa . It includes defective images classified into three categories: horizontal, vertical, and holes. Each defective image is accompanied by three corresponding mask images. The raw images are stored in a folder labeled *captured*, with each image having a resolution of 640×360 pixels.

Dataset from Peng et al. (2020) (59)

To supplement the dataset, the author of the study titled *Automatic Fabric Defect Detection Method Using Pran-Net* (Peng et al., 2020) was contacted. With permission, annotated non-defective images from their dataset were incorporated into this project.

Image Distribution Summary

After consolidating the data from all sources, the final dataset consisted of 2,739 images, distributed as follows:

- **Defect-free images:** 1,666
- **Defective images:** 1,073
 - Hole defects: 281
 - Horizontal defects: 136
 - Line defects: 157
 - Stain defects: 398
 - Vertical defects: 101

Total number of images used in this study is 2,739.

Fig. 3 Number of images in each class of the dataset

Figure 4: Number of images in each defect category

Experimental Setup and Evaluation

Image Configuration and Environment

Two image resolutions were chosen for experimentation:

- 150×700
- 245×345

All experiments were conducted using the Python programming language. The model development and training were carried out using Keras, with TensorFlow serving as the backend framework. Additional libraries, such as NumPy, Pandas, and Scikit-learn, were employed for data manipulation and evaluation. The entire workflow was implemented within the Visual Studio Code (VS Code) development environment.

Data Pre-processing

The dataset displayed a class imbalance between defective and defect-free samples. To address this, several sampling methods from the `imbalanced-learn` library were applied. These techniques were tested on both image dimensions (150×700 and 245×345) to identify the most effective approach for performance enhancement.

Data Visualization

To facilitate better understanding of the dataset, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was applied for dimensionality reduction and visualization. PCA simplifies high-dimensional data while preserving the maximum possible variance, making it ideal for visualizing complex structures in lower dimensions (typically 2D or 3D). This not only reveals hidden patterns and relationships but also helps in identifying redundant or noisy features that may hinder performance.

Model Architecture: Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)

A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) was designed for multi-class classification of fabric defects. The architecture includes five 2D convolutional layers, each responsible for extracting progressively abstract features.

- **Conv1:** 16 filters, kernel size 7×7
- **Conv2:** 32 filters, kernel size 5×5
- **Conv3:** 64 filters, kernel size 3×3
- **Conv4:** 128 filters, kernel size 3×3
- **Conv5:** 256 filters, kernel size 3×3

Each convolutional layer was configured with 'same' padding to preserve spatial dimensions, followed by the following components:

- **Batch Normalization:** Standardizes inputs for faster convergence.
- **Activation Function:** ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) applied for non-linearity.
- **Max Pooling:** 2×2 filters for dimensionality reduction and downsampling.
- **Dropout:** Introduced to mitigate overfitting by randomly deactivating neurons.

Following the convolutional layers, a **Flatten** layer was used to convert the feature maps into a 1D vector, suitable for the dense layers. The final fully connected (dense) layer employed a **SoftMax** activation function to produce a probability distribution over the defect classes.

Training and Evaluation Strategy

The model was compiled using the Adaptive Moment Estimation (**Adam**) optimizer, which combines the advantages of both RMSProp and momentum-based optimization strategies.

For training:

- The dataset was split using a stratified ratio of 95% training and 5% testing.
- Validation data was used during training to fine-tune hyperparameters.
- Training was conducted for 100 epochs with a batch size of 6.

A **10-fold stratified cross-validation** technique was used to assess the model's generalization ability. In each fold, a new CNN model was initialized and trained, and performance metrics (validation loss and accuracy) were recorded. This methodology ensures a robust and unbiased evaluation across different data partitions.

Evaluation Metrics

To comprehensively assess the performance of the proposed CNN model for fabric defect classification, a combination of standard evaluation metrics and time-based performance indicators was employed.

Classification Metrics

The following metrics were calculated using the confusion matrix to evaluate the model's predictive performance:

- **Accuracy:** Represents the ratio of correctly predicted instances to the total number of predictions. It is a global measure of model correctness.
- **Precision:** Measures the proportion of correctly predicted positive observations to the total predicted positives. It reflects the model's ability to avoid false positives.
- **Recall:** Also known as sensitivity, recall quantifies the proportion of actual positives that were correctly identified. It indicates the ability to minimize false negatives.
- **F1-Score:** The harmonic mean of precision and recall. This metric is particularly useful when class distribution is imbalanced, offering a balanced assessment.
- **Confusion Matrix:** Provides a tabulated summary of true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives for all classes. It offers detailed insights into the classification performance.

Time-Based Evaluation

In addition to classification accuracy, the model was evaluated based on time performance metrics, which are crucial for real-world deployment.

- **Validation Time:** This refers to the time taken to evaluate the model’s performance on the validation dataset after each training epoch. It includes the computation of evaluation metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. Validation time is critical for hyperparameter tuning and monitoring model generalization to prevent overfitting.
- **Modelling Time:** Also referred to as training time, this denotes the total duration required for training the model across all epochs. It encompasses the time consumed by both forward and backward propagation operations as the model optimizes its internal parameters. Efficient modelling time is essential when dealing with large datasets or complex architectures.
- **Prediction Time:** This is the duration required by the trained CNN model to make predictions on new, unseen data. It is a key metric for deployment scenarios, particularly in real-time applications where fast inference is necessary, such as automated quality inspection in textile manufacturing or live video analysis.

1 Results

The performance of the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) was evaluated on two image resolutions: 245×345 and 150×700 . Initially, the models were trained without applying any sampling techniques. Subsequently, a variety of sampling strategies from the `imbalanced-learn` module were applied to determine the most effective method for enhancing classification performance on imbalanced data.

1.1 Parameter Summary

Table 1 presents the total number of parameters (trainable and non-trainable) for the CNN models trained on the two image resolutions.

1.2 Performance Without and With Sampling Techniques

The model was evaluated using multiple sampling techniques, including both undersampling and oversampling methods. The goal was to improve performance on imbalanced datasets while maintaining a high classification accuracy.

Table 2 summarizes the model performance (Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-score) across different sampling techniques and image sizes.

1.3 Model Time Performance

The time performance of the CNN model was evaluated in three key areas:

- **Validation Time:** Time required to evaluate the model on the validation dataset.

Table 1: Trainable and non-trainable parameters for different image sizes

Image Size	Total Parameters	Trainable	Non-trainable
245×345	2,698,310	2,697,062	1,248
150×700	3,157,062	3,155,814	1,248

Table 2: Model performance using various sampling techniques

2*Sampling Technique	245×345				150×700			
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
No Sampling	94%	96%	94%	94%	91%	91%	91%	91%
Undersampling								
Cluster Centroids	89%	91%	89%	90%	73%	87%	73%	76%
AllKNN	93%	97%	93%	94%	94%	95%	94%	94%
Condensed Nearest Neighbor	65%	83%	65%	69%	69%	73%	69%	69%
Edited Nearest Neighbors	90%	93%	90%	89%	87%	91%	87%	87%
Repeated ENN	88%	90%	88%	88%	91%	93%	91%	91%
Instance Hardness Threshold	87%	88%	87%	87%	85%	87%	85%	86%
NearMiss	73%	87%	73%	75%	77%	85%	77%	78%
Neighborhood Cleaning Rule	95%	95%	95%	95%	91%	92%	91%	91%
Tomek Links	92%	93%	92%	92%	91%	91%	91%	90%
Random Undersampler	93%	94%	93%	93%	90%	93%	90%	90%
Oversampling								
ADASYN	95%	95%	95%	95%	90%	90%	90%	90%
Random Oversampling	96%	97%	96%	96%	95%	96%	95%	95%
Borderline SMOTE	96%	96%	96%	95%	93%	93%	93%	93%
KMeans SMOTE	94%	95%	94%	94%	95%	96%	95%	95%
SMOTEN	91%	92%	91%	91%	93%	94%	93%	93%
SVM SMOTE	96%	96%	96%	96%	95%	96%	96%	96%
Combined Sampling								
SMOTE-ENN	98%	98%	98%	98%	96%	96%	96%	96%
SMOTE-Tomek	96%	96%	96%	96%	96%	96%	96%	91%
Others								
Ensemble	91%	91%	91%	91%	-	-	-	-
Pipeline	93%	93%	93%	93%	87%	-	-	-
Function Sampler	94%	95%	94%	94%	96%	97%	96%	96%

- **Modeling Time:** Total training time taken by the model to learn from the training data.
- **Prediction Time:** Time taken by the trained model to predict class labels for unseen data.

These metrics were recorded for both image sizes (245×345 and 150×700) across various data preprocessing techniques. The results are summarized in Table 3.

Discussion

The primary objectives of this study were twofold: (1) to compile a robust image dataset containing examples of fabric defects, and (2) to develop a CNN-based classification model capable of accurately identifying these defects. The ultimate goal was to lay the foundation for an automated defect detection system suitable for textile industry applications.

To accomplish these aims, a dataset comprising 2,739 labeled images—1,666 non-defective and 1,073 defective—was constructed. Various state-of-the-art data sampling techniques were applied and evaluated using a custom convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture. These experiments yielded valuable insights regarding the impact of sampling strategies on model performance and computational efficiency.

Performance Without Sampling

As shown in Table 2, using the raw, imbalanced dataset negatively affected the model’s performance. For images sized at 150×700 , the CNN achieved 91% across accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. When the image size was reduced to 245×345 , the model’s performance improved, reaching 94% accuracy, 96% precision, and 94% recall and F1-score. These results indicate that the smaller image resolution yielded superior outcomes; however, further enhancement was necessary, prompting the application of sampling techniques.

Oversampling Techniques

As detailed in Table 2, oversampling strategies such as ADASYN, Random Oversampling, Borderline SMOTE, and SVM SMOTE significantly improved the model’s performance on the 245×345 image set. SMOTENC could not be executed due to memory constraints, while SMOTEN and kMeans SMOTE did not show substantial improvement.

Among these, Random Oversampling achieved the highest precision (97%) and demonstrated efficiency in terms of validation and modeling time. ADASYN also showed competitive results, with relatively short processing durations. Conversely, methods like Borderline SMOTE, SMOTEN, and kMeans SMOTE incurred longer execution times, particularly during the validation phase.

PCA Dimensionality Reduction

Fig. 4 PCA before data pre-processing

Figure 5: Sample output visualization

Data Visualization and Model Performance Analysis

Figure illustrates the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) visualization of the dataset prior to any preprocessing. In this figure, defect-free images are marked in red, while defective images are represented by various colors with dashed outlines: royal blue for holes, orange for vertical defects, green for lines, light blue for horizontal defects, and yellow for stains.

It is evident from Figure that the defect classes are not distinctly separated. For example, yellow dots (stains) overlap with red dots (defect-free), increasing the likelihood of misclassification. Similarly, royal blue (holes) and green (lines) dots intermingle, further complicating accurate defect classification.

Figures and present PCA visualizations after applying the best performing sampling technique, SMOTEENN, on image sizes 245×345 and 150×700 respectively. As shown in Figure 7, there is a clear separation between defect classes, contributing to improved classification accuracy. Although Figure ?? shows similar segregation, minor overlaps persist, such as red dots partially blending with other classes.

Figure 8 depicts PCA visualizations for additional resampling methods including SMOTETomek, SVM SMOTE, Random Oversampling, Borderline SMOTE, and Function Sampler for various image sizes. The red dots (defect-free class) appear mixed with other classes across these techniques, explaining the reduced accuracy observed in these cases.

PCA serves as an effective diagnostic tool to visualize model performance by clearly representing the multi-class classification behavior.

Figure 6: PCA visualization before data preprocessing, showing poor class separation.

Figure 7: PCA after preprocessing with SMOTEENN: (a) Image size 245×345 , (b) Image size 150×700 .

Figure 8: PCA after preprocessing with various sampling techniques: SMOTE-Tomek, SVM SMOTE, Random Oversampling, Borderline SMOTE, Function Sampler.

Figure 9 shows the confusion matrix of the CNN model trained with SMOTEENN for image size 245×345 . Figure 10 presents the corresponding prediction time and accuracy, demonstrating that the CNN model achieves 100% accuracy in defect classification with minimal prediction time.

Figure 9: Confusion matrix for CNN model with SMOTEENN sampling, image size 245×345 .

Literature Review and Model Verification

Our experimental findings corroborate the observations made by Luke, Joseph, and Balaji (2019), which include:

1. CNN performance is significantly influenced by image resolution.
2. Image size substantially impacts model accuracy, with size changes either enhancing or impairing performance.
3. Accuracy generally improves with larger image sizes but may decline beyond an optimal threshold due to a reduced receptive field.
4. Larger image sizes affect the network’s ability to learn medium- and high-level features.
5. Optimal accuracy is achieved with image sizes between the default and 512 pixels.
6. Resizing images may cause loss of low-level feature information, influencing accuracy, especially for inter-class similarities.

Thambawita et al. (2021) (62) demonstrated superior CNN performance with 512×512 images compared to 32×32 . Conversely, Horwath et al. (2020) noted challenges in segmenting high-resolution images due to difficulties in distinguishing interface pixels from the background.

Sabottke and Spieler (2020) highlighted the balance between model complexity and overfitting risk, concluding that resolutions between 256×256 and

Figure 10: Prediction time and accuracy of CNN model with SMOTEENN for image size 245×345 .

448×448 yield optimal CNN performance. They also discussed trade-offs between image resolution and feasible batch sizes, emphasizing that optimization complexity affects model accuracy beyond overfitting concerns.

Rukundo (2021) observed that training with 256×256 images led to lower cross-entropy loss and higher accuracy compared to 128×128 images in U-net models.

Comparison with Related Works

Historically, fabric defect detection has been predominantly manual. Although several automated algorithms exist, they suffer from slow processing speeds and limited defect coverage, restricting practical industrial adoption.

Table 5 summarizes performance metrics of key related models alongside our proposed model. While Zhao et al. (2019) achieved superior accuracy and speed using CNN-VLSTM, their approach is sensitive to complex fabric structures and involves higher model complexity.

Unlike Zhao et al. (2019), who reported best results with a small 500-image dataset, our CNN model performs better using a larger dataset of 2,739 images, particularly at image size 245×345 , making it more practical for industrial applications.

Cheng et al. (2022) evaluated SCUNet on a small grayscale dataset (106 images) with single image size 256×256 , focusing on plain fabric and ignoring colored or patterned fabrics. They also did not report detection times, unlike our work, which covers a wider range of fabric types and defect sizes and includes both color and grayscale images. Our model achieves 98% accuracy and recall, demonstrating greater versatility and real-world applicability.

Conclusion

This research presents an innovative approach for the automated detection of fabric defects in the textile industry. The textile production process starts with yarn from the spinning department, which is woven into greige fabric. This fabric then undergoes various finishing processes such as scouring, bleaching, dyeing, and final finishing. Once the fabric reaches the finished state, it undergoes quality inspection before moving to the stitching department for garment production. Traditionally, quality inspection involves manual examination on quality tables, where inspectors identify and mark any fabric defects—a labor-intensive and time-consuming task.

The primary objective of this study was to identify an effective deep learning algorithm to automate fabric quality inspection, thereby replacing the manual

process. Following an extensive literature review, a convolutional neural network (CNN) was selected as the foundation for this work. Two image sizes— 150×700 and 245×345 —were tested to determine the optimal size for model performance. Additionally, several sampling techniques were evaluated to address the challenge of dataset imbalance.

The results demonstrated that the CNN model combined with the SMO-TEENN sampling technique produced the best performance, representing a significant advancement in automating fabric defect detection. Image size was found to have a considerable impact on model accuracy, with the 245×345 size outperforming the larger 150×700 images.

From a practical standpoint, the model also exhibited fast processing speeds, making it well-suited for industrial deployment. Specifically, for the 245×345 image size, the model achieved a validation time of 3.4 seconds and a prediction time of just 0.09 seconds, compared to 3.5 and 1.15 seconds, respectively, for the 150×700 size. These results highlight the model’s potential as an efficient and reliable solution for real-time fabric quality inspection in textile manufacturing.

Deployment Strategy

A novel approach is proposed to revolutionize the fabric quality inspection process. This method integrates the use of an infrared camera that scans the entire fabric width as it moves along the length of the inspection table. The camera captures high-resolution infrared images, which serve as input for the developed machine learning algorithm tasked with identifying fabric defects.

Upon detecting a defect, the algorithm triggers an automatic labeling machine to mark the defective section on the fabric. The entire workflow of this automated inspection system is illustrated in Figure 11.

	Accuracy %	Precision %	Recall %	F1 Score %	Detection Time
Peng et. al (2020) PRAN-NET Denim	91.99				9.7 Frame per sec
Peng et. al (2020) PRAN-NET Plain	98.66				25.4 Frame per sec
Almeida, Moutinho and Matus-Carvalho (2021) CNN-FN Reduction	75.45	72.76	88.47		5.69 ms per image
Zhao et. al (2019) CNN-VLSTM	95.73-99.47	95.74-100	95.73-100	95.73-100	1.8-3.5 e2
Wei et. al (2019) Faster RCNN	95.88				0.3 sec
Liu et al. (2019) VGG16	97.7				
Liu et al. (2019) LZFNet	98				13.8 ms
Cheng et al. (2022) SCUNet	98.01		96.86		
Our Model	98	98	98	98	0.06-0.07 sec

Table 5 Performance comparison of different models from the literature review with our model

Figure 11: Automated Fabric Defect Detection Workflow

2 Future Research

Further research is necessary to improve the robustness of the model by expanding the image dataset and incorporating a wider variety of defect types for multi-class classification. Additionally, more comprehensive studies are required to facilitate the practical deployment of this model within the textile industry. This would involve the integration of infrared cameras and defect labeling machines to achieve a fully automated fabric quality inspection process. Such efforts will significantly contribute to the complete adoption of the developed algorithm in industrial environments.

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Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares no conflict of interest.

Appendix B - Figures

- Fig. 1: Fabric manufacturing process
- Fig. 2: Difference between ADASYN and SMOTE algorithms (?)
- Fig. 3: Number of images in each class of the dataset
- Fig. 4: PCA before data pre-processing
- Fig. 5: PCA after data pre-processing with SMOTEENN sampling technique
- Fig. 6: PCA after data pre-processing with:
 - a) SMOTETomek (245x345)
 - b) SVM SMOTE Oversampling (245x345)
 - c) SVM SMOTE Oversampling (150x700)
 - d) Random Oversampling (245x345)
 - e) Random Oversampling (150x700)
 - f) Borderline SMOTE (245x345)
 - g) Function Sampler (150x700)

- Fig. 7: Confusion matrices of the CNN model sampled with SMOTEENN method
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Appendix C - Tables

- Table 1: Total number of trainable and non-trainable parameters for the two image sizes
- Table 2: Model performance without and with data pre-processing
- Table 3: Model time performance with data pre-processing
- Table 4: Performance comparison of the best performing sampling techniques
- Table 5: Performance comparison of different models from the literature review with our model
- Table 6: Performance metrics of Zhao et al. (2019) model

Appendix D - Sampling Techniques (PCA, Confusion Matrix)

Undersampling Techniques

AIKNN

Image sizes: 245x345, 150x700

Cluster Centroids

Image sizes: 245x345, 150x700

Condensed Nearest Neighbour

Image sizes: 245x345, 150x700

Edited Nearest Neighbour

Image sizes: 245x345, 150x700

Instance Hardness Threshold

Image sizes: 245x345, 150x700

NearMiss

Image sizes: 245x345, 150x700

Neighbourhood Cleaning Rule

Image sizes: 245x345, 150x700

Random Undersampler

Image sizes: 245x345, 150x700

Repeated Edited Nearest Neighbour

Image sizes: 245x345, 150x700

Tomek Links

Image sizes: 245x345, 150x700

Oversampling Techniques

ADASYN

Image sizes: 245x345, 150x700

Borderline SMOTE

Image sizes: 245x345, 150x700

kMeans SMOTE

Image sizes: 245x345, 150x700

Random Oversampling

Image sizes: 245x345, 150x700

SMOTEN

Image sizes: 245x345, 150x700

Combined Oversampling and Undersampling

SMOTETomek

Image sizes: 245x345, 150x700

Ensemble

Pipeline

Image sizes: 245x345, 150x700

Miscellaneous

Function Sampler

Image sizes: 245x345, 150x700

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Table 3: Model time performance (in seconds) across different sampling techniques

2*Sampling Technique	245×345			150×700		
	Validation Time	Model Time	Prediction Time	Validation Time	Model Time	Prediction Time
No Sampling	2.64	0.22	0.06	3.26	0.34	0.06-0.10
Undersampling						
Cluster Centroids	2.80	0.29	0.06-0.10	3.11	0.205	0.07-0.08
AllKNN	2.69	0.21	0.07	3.52	0.24	0.07-0.08
Condensed Nearest Neighbor	2.52	0.20	0.07	3.18	0.20	0.06-0.15
Edited Nearest Neighbors	2.50	0.20	0.09	3.30	0.22	0.09
Repeated ENN	2.60	0.20	0.06	3.12	0.21	0.05-0.70
Instance Hardness Threshold	2.50	0.21	0.07	3.32	0.20	0.08
NearMiss	2.69	0.24	0.07	3.20	0.20	0.07
Neighborhood Cleaning Rule	2.82	0.24	0.07	3.40	0.25	0.06-0.14
Tomek Links	2.45	0.27	0.06-0.10	2.93	0.30	0.08-0.10
Random Undersampler	2.55	0.23	0.06-0.08	3.86	2.51	0.09
Oversampling						
ADASYN	2.43	0.56	0.08-0.10	3.53	0.89	0.08
Random Oversampling	2.90	0.70	0.06-0.10	2.98	0.23	0.07
Borderline SMOTE	3.25	1.96	0.06-0.096	3.31	1.74	0.065-0.087
KMeans SMOTE	3.20	1.10	0.09	3.47	5.66	0.077
SMOTEN	3.00	1.90	0.07	3.36	2.02	0.07-0.09
SVM SMOTE	3.15	1.90	0.085-0.10	3.40	1.86	0.07-0.086
Combined Sampling						
SMOTE-ENN	3.40	1.57	0.09	3.50	1.15	0.07-0.10
SMOTE-Tomek	2.77	2.21	0.06	3.67	2.44	0.07-0.12
Ensemble						
Pipeline (AllKNN + NCL)	2.80	0.31	0.07	3.26	0.35	0.06-0.09
Miscellaneous						
Function Sampler	2.59	0.21	0.07-0.10	3.26	0.20	0.07-0.15

Table 4: Performance Comparison of Best Performing Sampling Techniques

Sampling Method	Image Size	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	Model Time (s)	Predict Time (s)	Validation Time (s)
Oversampling and Undersampling								
SMOTEENN	245×345	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	1.57	0.09	3.40
	150×700	0.96	0.96	0.96	0.96	1.15	0.07-0.10	3.50
SMOTETomek	245×345	0.96	0.96	0.96	0.96	2.21	0.06	2.77
Oversampling								
SVM SMOTE	245×345	0.96	0.96	0.96	0.96	1.90	0.09-0.10	3.15
	150×700	0.95	0.96	0.95	0.95	1.86	0.07-0.09	3.40
Random Oversampling	245×345	0.96	0.97	0.96	0.96	0.70	0.06-0.10	2.90
	150×700	0.95	0.96	0.95	0.95	0.23	0.07	2.98
Borderline SMOTE	245×345	0.96	0.96	0.96	0.95	1.96	0.06-0.09	3.25
Miscellaneous								
Function Sampler	150×700	0.96	0.97	0.96	0.96	0.20	0.07-0.15	3.26

Table 5: Performance Comparison of Related Models and Our Proposed Model

Model	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1 Score (%)	Detection Time
Peng et al. (2020) PRAN-NET Denim	91.99	-	-	-	9.7 frames/sec
Peng et al. (2020) PRAN-NET Plain	98.66	-	-	-	25.4 frames/sec
Almeida et al. (2021) CNN-FN Reduction	75.45	72.76	88.47	-	5.69 ms/image
Zhao et al. (2019) CNN-VLSTM	95.73-99.47	95.74-100	95.73-100	95.73-100	1.8-3.5 s
Wei et al. (2019) Faster RCNN	95.88	-	-	-	0.3 s
Liu et al. (2019) VGG16	97.7	-	-	-	-
Liu et al. (2019) LZFFNet	98.0	-	-	-	13.8 ms
Cheng et al. (2022) SCUNet	98.01	96.86	-	-	-
Our Model (CNN + SMOTEENN)	98	98	98	98	0.06-0.07 s